

Metal Complexes as Ligands. Trinuclear Alkali Metal Complexes with Copper(II) and Nickel(II) Acetylacetonates

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The copper(II) and nickel(II) acetylacetonates $[M_a(acac)_2]$ have been used as double-faced ligands (complex ligand) in the synthesis of novel trinuclear alkali metal complexes of the general formula $[M_a(acac)_2(M_bL)_2]$, where $M_a = Cu^{II}$ and Ni^{II} ; $M_bL = Li, Na$ or K salt of the deprotonated 8-hydroxyquinoline, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, *o*-nitrophenol and anthranilic acid. On the basis of magnetic, ir, and electronic spectral data, the attachment of alkali metal ions through the oxygen atoms of carbonyl group of acetylacetonates, have been suggested.

IN our previous communication¹, we described the synthesis of oxygen bridged binuclear alkali metal complexes using 'metal complexes' as ligands, having phenolic oxygen atoms. On the basis of ir spectra, magnetic properties and electronic spectral studies, the coordination of alkali metals through two phenolic oxygen atoms, have been suggested. In view of our success in synthesising these oxygen bridged binuclear alkali metal complexes, it was desired to extend the investigation by selecting bivalent acetylacetonates as the 'complex ligand' $[Cu(acac)_2]$ and $[Ni(acac)_2]$. The structure of $Cu(acac)_2$ and $[Ni(acac)_2]_3$ have been well established²⁻⁴.

Experimental

The usual method of synthesis was to take the metal complexes in absolute ethanol and alkali metal salts were added to it in the ratio of 1 : 1. It was refluxed with constant stirring on a hot-plate for 2-3 h. The whole thing went into solution and the adducts were precipitated in hot condition during reflux. The product was cooled, filtered, washed with absolute ethanol and dried in an air-oven at 90°.

Results and Discussion

The adducts are stable under dry condition, but decompose on exposure to moisture; as such, were kept in a desiccator over solid anhydrous $CaCl_2$. The adducts are slightly soluble in benzene and ethanol without decomposition. The colour, decomposition temperature and analytical values of these adducts are in Table 1.

Ir spectra: Infrared spectral measurements were made in nujol for the ligands and complexes in the range 4000-650 cm^{-1} . Selected bands are given in Table 1. The most important feature is

that there are important differences between the ir spectra of $Cu(acac)_2$ and $[Ni(acac)_2]_3$, and the trinuclear complexes formed when they function as a ligand. It has been observed⁵ that when the transition metal acetylacetonate complex is in a monomeric state, the $C=O$ stretching frequency lies in the range 1580-1555 cm^{-1} . In case of $[Ni(acac)_2]_3$, which is a trimer, this $C=O$ frequency splits into two⁶, one at 1595 cm^{-1} and the other at 1560 cm^{-1} . Looking into the crystal structure of the trimer, it has been found that half the oxygen atoms are bridged oxygens (with coordination number three), one oxygen atom attached to two Ni^{II} ions. The other six oxygen atoms (with coordination number two), are attached to only one Ni^{II} ion. These latter six $C=O$ seem to be normal ones and fall in the range of monomers (1580-1555 cm^{-1}). Owing to the bridging character of the former six oxygens, when one oxygen is donating electrons to two Ni^{II} ions, the $C=O$ frequency shifted to higher frequency at 1595 cm^{-1} .

The Co^{II} - and Mn^{II} -acetylacetonates are also polynuclear and have those, two $C=O$ frequencies reported, the one normal at 1560 and 1565 cm^{-1} , and the other, the bridged one at 1588 and 1605 cm^{-1} , respectively. The position of $C=O$ bands of some metal-acetylacetonates is shown in Table 2. One can thus generalise that in monomeric metal-acetylacetonates, the $C=O$ band is below 1580 cm^{-1} ; whereas in polymers with oxygen bridges, the $C=O$ frequency splits into two, the one higher, above 1580 cm^{-1} (due to bridging) and the other lower, below 1580 cm^{-1} . In these polynuclear alkali metal-transition metal acetylacetonates, the $C=O$ frequencies have been observed not in their normal range, but invariably higher between 1580 and 1600 cm^{-1} . This is very suggestive that all these oxygens are bridged ones,

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA

Compd *	Colour	Decomp. temp. °C	Analysis : Found/(Calcd.)			$\nu_{C=O}$ cm ⁻¹	Magnetic moment at 300 K B.M.
			N	Cu/Ni	Alkali metal		
Cu(acac) ₂ [†]	Blue	240				1 577s	2.1
Cu(acac) ₂ (Li8HQ) ₂	Yellowish green	260	4.94 (4.98)	11.62 (11.30)	—	1 590s	2.1
Cu(acac) ₂ (Na8HQ) ₂	Yellowish green	250	4.56 (4.71)	11.10 (10.69)	7.26 (7.75)	1 590s	2.2
Cu(acac) ₂ (K8HQ) ₂	Yellowish green	258	4.54 (4.46)	11.00 (10.11)	13.10 (12.40)	1 590s	2.1
Cu(acac) ₂ (Li1N2N) ₂	Brown	255	4.89 (4.51)	10.62 (10.25)	—	1 590s	2.1
Cu(acac) ₂ (Na1N2N) ₂	Brown	255	3.99 (4.29)	9.80 (9.70)	7.60 (7.06)	1 595s	2.1
Cu(acac) ₂ (K1N2N) ₂	Brown	250	4.00 (4.09)	10.10 (9.29)	11.70 (11.41)	1 590s	2.1
Ni(acac) ₂ [†]	Green	191				1 595s, 1 560s	3.2
Ni(acac) ₂ (Li8HQ) ₂	Light green	325	5.34 (3.01)	10.92 (10.50)	—	1 585s	3.9
Ni(acac) ₂ (Na8HQ) ₂	Light green	320	4.62 (4.74)	10.30 (9.93)	7.80 (7.78)	1 590s	3.9
Ni(acac) ₂ (K8HQ) ₂	Light green	325	5.46 (5.35)	11.64 (11.23)	14.80 (14.90)	1 585s	4.0
Ni(acac) ₂ (Li1N2N) ₂	Brown	310	4.84 (4.55)	10.26 (9.54)	—	1 585s	3.8
Ni(acac) ₂ (Na1N2N) ₂	Brown	305	4.62 (4.31)	10.20 (9.01)	7.20 (7.10)	1 585s	3.8
Ni(acac) ₂ (K1N2N) ₂	Brown	310	4.26 (4.12)	9.01 (8.60)	11.38 (11.40)	1 580s	3.9
Ni(acac) ₂ (NaONP) ₂	Light yellow	310	4.69 (4.80)	10.96 (10.14)	7.94 (7.95)	1 585s	4.0
Ni(acac) ₂ (Na.anth) ₂	Greenish white	305	5.32 (4.87)	10.64 (10.21)	8.10 (8.00)	1 590s	3.9

*8HQ = Deprotonated 8-hydroxyquinoline; 1N2N = deprotonated 1-nitroso-2-naphthol; ONP = deprotonated *o*-nitrophenol; anth = deprotonated anthranilic acid.

s = Strong

bridging the transition metal and most probably the alkali metals.

TABLE 2—POSITION OF C=O FREQUENCY IN SOME METAL-ACETYLACETONATES⁵ NEAR 1 500–1 600 cm⁻¹

Metal acetylacetonate	Nature	C—O (in cm ⁻¹)
Cr ^{III}	Monomeric	1 570s
Mn ^{III}	Monomeric	1 562s
Fe ^{III}	Monomeric	1 565s
Co ^{III}	Monomeric	1 568s
Ga ^{III}	Monomeric	1 580s
Fe ^{II}	Monomeric	1 580s
Cu ^{II}	Monomeric	1 580s
M ^{II}	Polymeric	1 605s, 1 565s
Co ^{II}	Polymeric	1 588s, 1 560s
N ^{II}	Polymeric	1 595s, 1 560s

s = Strong absorption

Magnetic property: Magnetic measurements were taken on a Cahn Faraday balance at 300 K, and the values are given in Table 1. The magnetic moment of Cu(acac)₂ is 2.1 B.M., and the values of

the adducts also lie in the same region, suggesting the same square-planar geometry. 3.2 B.M. value for [Ni(acac)₂]₂ suggest an octahedral structure, supported by X ray⁷.

The magnetic moment values of alkali metal complexes from [Ni(acac)₂]₂ are in the range of 3.8–4.0 B.M., which is higher than the values of nickel-acetylacetonate. These high values may be due to the change in the geometry of Ni(acac)₂ in the adducts, from an octahedral to tetrahedral structure. As a result of complexation with alkali metal salts with bulky anions, the polymerised system of [Ni(acac)₂]₂ might undergo a break due to steric hindrance, a result of overcrowding of mutually repelling negative field of anions in the vicinity of each other. A break in the polymerised system would evidently lead the central metal ion Ni^{II} to four-coordination number and assume a tetrahedral structure.

Electronic spectra: All electronic spectra were recorded on a Varian Carry-14 spectrophotometer in nujol. The electronic spectra of the copper-adducts were not studied in detail as the interpretation is somewhat complicated due to the distorted

octahedral and square-planar coordination of Cu^{2+} . The visible absorption spectra of $[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2]_3$ show the typical octahedral Ni^{2+} absorptions at about 400, 600 and 960 nm. The corresponding alkali metal adducts show only one absorption at about 650 nm, the other two being absent. Further, they show a small hump at about 1200 nm. The nature of band, together with the magnetic moment values of nickel-adducts, suggest a tetrahedral structure.

Structure and bonding : The magnetic properties and electronic spectral studies of alkali metal adducts reveal a break in the polymerised system of $[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2]_3$. Accordingly, the polymeric octahedral structure of $[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2]_3$ is converted into a tetrahedral monomer of $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2$ in alkali metal adducts. The bonding between metal acetylacetonates is most likely through the oxygen atoms of carbonyl group, tetrahedrally situated in the case of nickel-adducts and square-planar in the case of $\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2$.

Where, $M_b = \text{Li, Na, K}$; and $L =$ deprotonated 8HQ and 1N2N.

Where, $M_b = \text{Li, Na, K}$; and $L =$ deprotonated 1N2N, ONP, 8HQ, anthranilic acid.

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